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ARAB CONNECTIONS AND UPSURGE OF INSURGENCY IN AFRICA: CASE-STUDY OF BOKO HARAM IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT: There has been a dramatic increase in intra-state conflicts in Africa and many countries in Africa have experienced an upsurge of insurgency within their territories. This paper begins with the history of insurgency in Africa and delves into the causes of the upsurge of insurgency in the continent in recent times with particular reference to the *Boko Haram* menace within Nigeria. The paper traces the origin of *Boko Haram* and probes into its links with international terrorist organizations like Al-Qaeda in the Lands of the Islamic Maghreb (AQIM) and *al-Shabaab* in Somalia. Using religious imperialism as the framework, the paper concludes that the *Boko Haram* insurgency is inspired by *jihadi-Salafi* ideology espoused by Saudi Arabia and is the last stage of the long drawn attempt to Islamize Nigeria. Only if the Nigerian government with international cooperation takes serious proactive steps to end *Boko Haram's* menace, it can also stem the rise of other regional Islamic fundamentalist insurgencies in the future.

Introduction

The history of insurgent uprising in Africa started with the *Mau-Mau* peasant revolt in Kenya in 1952. The *Mau-Mau* revolt was as a result "of economic and social disaffection in rural areas combined with the political radicalism of Nairobi" (Heather, 1999: p.1). Since then insurgent confrontations have been on the increase on the African continent especially in recent times.

Some of these wars have had negative reverberations on the continent that transcend national boundaries. Every year, thousands of lives are lost in Africa because of armed conflict: the Council on Foreign Relations (2012: p1) estimates the death toll due to armed conflict at about 250,000 per year. Perry (2011: p.1-2) has chronicled a list of terrorist activities in the continent in recent times to include the kidnapping of a Swede, a Dutch and a South African from a restaurant in Timbuktu, the killing of a German and the abduction of two French geologists in Mali, plus *al-Shabab's* war against the official government in Somalia and its protectors (African Union soldiers from Uganda and Burundi) with several grenade attacks by *al-Shabab* suicide-bombers in Kenya that killed 76 people in the Ugandan capital, Kampala in July 2010.

This has led to a redefinition in a negative image for Africa as a continent that is perpetually at war: a land of "...'evil', 'danger', 'criminality', 'disease', 'disorder', 'anarchy' and 'mindless violence' (Omeje, 2007: p.101). As such, Africa's unique history as the cradle of civilization has been obliterated today by these internecine wars in various parts of the continent. Thus, according to Irele (1999: p.100):

The visual image that is beamed on television across the world about Africa is that of a continent embroiled in fratricidal wars that are ethnically motivated. This image has become the predominant signifier of the continent's woes presented by the Western media for their viewer's consumption. Again and again, in newscasts about Africa, one encounters this image in their monotonous regularity and the image has become so pervasive and fixed in people's sub-consciousness to the extent that it has become the generative source of all ideas about the entire continent.

This problem has portrayed Africa to the outside world as a continent pervaded with "...poverty, diseases, civil disturbances, revolt, insurgency, guerrilla warfare, domestic rebellion and in recent time terrorism..." (Ogundiya, 2010: p.1). This informs the post 9/11 re-securization of Africa by the West as a zone of terror (Omeje, 2007: p.93). According to him (Omeje, 2007: p.102), "Africa is increasingly securitized as a zone of terror in the U.S. ..." Quoting Keenan (2004b) and Diallo (2005), Omeje (2007: p.102) noted that "senior officials of U.S. European Command (EUCOM), senior U.S. government officials, CIA counter-intelligence reports and Western media have played a big part in the redefinition of Africa as a potential breeding ground for Islamist militancy and a safe-haven for terrorists..."

Although most authors have attributed these recurrent spates of violence on the continent to ethnic rivalries and the failures of African governments, the major cause of frequent uprisings in Africa must be sought also outside the continent, while it cannot however be denied that in most countries of Africa, the state has reneged on its responsibility in the social contract, which is the basis upon which patriotism is founded (Achebe, 1984: p.15). This is just a part of the explanation for insurgent violence against governments of such states, including Nigeria, where violence is traceable to one section that has some connection with the Arab world, while other sections not having close affinities with the Arab world and whose people are living under the same conditions wrought by failed government remain peaceful and devoid of insurgent uprisings.

Statement of the Problem

Twenty-First Century Africa has been rebranded as a continent ridden with insurgency and a breeding ground for terrorists and suicide-bombers. This unfortunate appellation is due to the ubiquity of insurgent uprisings in the continent in recent times. However, such rebranding is a very wide generalization as there remain some parts of Africa that are not beleaguered by this blight.

Arab North Africa has witnessed the greatest occurrences of insurgent movements compared to Black Africa south of the Sahara. The greatest factor that has amplified the upsurge of insurgency in Africa is the Arab connection. The trade and most importantly, the religious relations of North Africa with the Arab world have contributed to the increasing manifestation of insurgency in this part of the continent and a consequent destabilization of the entire continent through agents from this geographic section. For instance, the "Arab Springs" spilled over into North Africa and resulted in the Algerian students' protest against the government of Abdellaziz Bouteflika in April 2011. This reverberated into Egypt and other parts of Africa.

Extremism and terrorism in North Africa seems to have reached alarming proportions. Quoting Mazrui (2005: p.15) and Keenan (2004a), Omeje (2007: p.102) shows that "the new realization that there are large Muslim population in Africa north of the equator (West Africa, Sahel-Arab Maghreb and Horn of Africa) has suddenly fuelled disquieting discourses of anger and terror in the West since the commencement of the global war on terror." CSIS (2010: p.2) reported that North African terrorism which was largely directed at domestic governments in the 1990s has later assumed the international dimensions of today, with Arab terrorists from Iraq, Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia and Libya have been known to have sponsored or be directly involved in terrorist activities in Europe, etc. Until the 2007 United States' strikes against "al-Qaeda in Iraq", faction-ridden Iraq seemed to have become the breeding-ground also for North African terrorist's groups. It projected some local insurgent groups like the Salafi Group for Preaching and Combat (GSPC) into international terrorist limelight, it provided a stream of suicide-bombers with logistics and became the rallying point and

recruitment center for the training of jihadists to be set to Europe and America. Iraq therefore provided the “fateful triangle” [à la Professor Jean-Pierre Filiu] between North Africa, Europe and Iraq (CSIS, 2010: p.2).

The defeat of al-Qaeda in Iraq witnessed the later metamorphosis of the Algerian GPSC into the “Al-Qaeda in the Lands of the Islamic Maghreb” (AQIM). According to U.S. Ambassador Robert Godec, Deputy-Coordinator for Counter-Terrorism at the State Department, as quoted by CSIS (2010: p.3), AQIM is “today, the biggest terrorist challenge facing the Maghreb... and in terms of statements, strategy and tactics, AQIM’s behavior mimics that of al-Qaeda generally.” The report went further to show that “AQIM operates, recruits and plans in ungoverned spaces, launches attacks against both civilians and military targets and kidnaps Westerners. In approving the creation of AQIM, al-Qaeda’s central leadership hoped that Algeria would become another center of the global jihad”.

The desire of AQIM and other insurgent groups therefore is to internationalize terror. Unfortunately, the defeat of their global goal through U.S. military efforts has led these groups to shift the focus of their operations to regions and specific strategic countries through which they could ultimately achieve their long term goal of global coverage. This informs the rise of Boko Haram in Nigeria.

Research Methodology and Theoretical Framework

The methodology used for this study is descriptive analysis based on secondary data. It drew inspiration from published and unpublished materials such as international, national, governmental, semi-governmental, private corporate bodies, expert committee and commission, newspaper and magazine reports, books, as well as research reports. Some of the reports consulted include annually, quarterly, monthly, fortnightly, weekly and daily published works by organizations like:

- Center for Strategic and International Studies
- United Nations Organization
- Local and International Dailies, etc.

Other sources consulted include published research work by scholars on the upsurge of insurgencies in Africa and the Boko Haram in Nigeria in particular. Some unpublished research works were also consulted in the course of the study.

One of the major causes of problems in Africa is the imperialist exploits of the continent, especially religious imperialism. Some of the alien religions that have been brought to Africa have had negative swelling impact on the continent.

Imperialism has diverse strands including political imperialism, economic imperialism, religious imperialism, cultural imperialism and assimilative imperialism, etc. Of all these forms of imperialism, religious imperialism seems to be more subtle than the other forms of imperialism because it reinforces the other forms, especially, cultural imperialism and assimilative imperialism.

Religion, it would be agreed, is part of the culture of its originators and therefore it carries in its spread the threads of such culture. Religious imperialism seeks to “civilize” the target population based on the claim of the superiority of the object of worship. Religious imperialists therefore disparage the object of worship of the target population and thereby brand them as “idol worshippers”, “barbarians”, “unbelievers” or the extreme of “infidels”. Being redefined as “barbarians”, the target population is regarded as “semi-humans”, inferior spiritually, morally and even intellectually and socially. Therefore, religious imperialists feel “compelled” to convert them to their religion in order to “civilize” them. Where they resist conversion, some religion, like Islam, encourages the bloody elimination of “infidels”.

The process of conversion involves the transmission of the tenets of a particular faith to the prospective converts. Such transmission most of the time takes place in the language of the imperialists.

With language which is a part of the culture of the imperialist forces, a wholesale transmission of the culture of the imperialists takes place. The end result is that, the convert is dispossessed, not only of his original object of worship, but of his original personality and character which are transformed into copies of the imperialists. According to Maunier (1949: p.184), this results in assimilation or assimilative imperialism. The overall effect is that the people are disinherited: they begin to feel that they no longer belong to the nationality of their forebears, and so disparage their origins and believe they belong to, become more loyal to and receive and act on the basis of the instructions of the imperialists.

This seems to validate Karl Marx assertion that religion is the opiate of the people and is also the explanation for the allegiance and sympathy Africans north of the Sahara manifest towards Arab cause.

Origins of Boko Haram

Boko Haram was founded in 2002 in Maiduguri by a radical Islamic cleric, Mohammad Yusuf with the official Arabic name of جماعة أهل نة س ال لدعوة ل جهاد وال translated as Jama'atul Alhul Sunnah Lidda'wati wal jihad, which means "People Committed to the Propagation of the Prophet's Teachings and Jihad" (Johnson, 2011). But over the years, the name Boko Haram, meaning "Western Education is Sin" has supplanted the official name of the group. This name, as reported in Ngex (2012), is believed to have been given as a label to this extremist group by the immediate community of Maiduguri, in Bornu State, where the group was founded as a result of Yusuf's abhorrence of anything Western. The sect however has since accepted this name in their official nomenclature.

However, others say that the label Boko Haram is just a cover name to confuse, mislead or a calculated attempt to deceive the public on the main aim of the organization (Usman, 2011), beyond the implication that the group's major goal should be the eradication of Western Education or its structures. Instead, the group's targets to date and main intention according to Ngex (2012) are that: "...Some of the group's recent attacks, like the bombing of a United Nations (U.N.) building in Abuja, seem to suggest that the group's ambitions are broader than initially believed..." Thus, Johnson (2011) and Ngex (2012) affirm that the acknowledged goal of the Boko Haram is: "to establish a fully Islamic state in Nigeria, including the implementation of criminal Sharia courts across the country".

It would be agreed that such imposing goals and the magnitude of terrorist activities carried out by the group to date can neither be conceived nor achieved by a group that is largely without an organized structure. This fact suggests that there may be some form of invisible hand outside the group that is controlling its operations from behind the scenes.

Boko Haram's Massacres in Nigeria

Since 2009, Boko Haram has been terrorizing Nigeria by bombing churches, in particular and attacking other public institutions, including the U.N. building in Abuja in August 2011. In an apparent underestimation of the group's capability and range at its inception, President Goodluck Jonathan promised to deal decisively with the terrorists, which he called "a faceless group of enemies of our democracy and prosperity of our nation..." (AFP, 2012). In reaction to the President's threat, the group's current leader, Abubakar Shekau, according to a report in the Journal of Turkish News (2012), released a 14-minute YouTube video calling the President's reaction as an empty threat. To make good his words, the Boko Haram terrorists began to carry out a number of suicide-bombings and assassinations from Maiduguri to Abuja. A chronological account of the terrorist activities of the group from 2009 to January 2012 reported by Ngex (2012) include: the refusal of Boko Haram members in June 2009 to follow a motor-bike helmet law which resulted in clashes with joint military and police patrol and 17 Boko Haram

members killed. In reaction, Mohammed Yusuf released another video to the President in which he threatened revenge attacks.

In July 2009, Boko Haram attacked Maiduguri police stations where hundreds were killed. In September 2010, Boko Haram members attacked a prison in Bauchi and freed hundreds of prisoners, including about 100 Boko Haram prisoners. In December 2010, the group carried out an attack on Army barracks in Abuja. In December 2010, they bombed strategic places in both Jos, Plateau State and in Maiduguri, Borno State, killing about 80 people. In December 2010, a Governorship candidate of the All Nigeria Peoples Party (ANPP) in Borno State and 7 others were shot dead by gunmen suspected to be Boko Haram members. In May 2011, Boko Haram carried out bomb attacks in several states after President Goodluck Jonathan's inauguration. In June 2011, the Police Headquarters in Abuja was bombed. In June 2011, Ibrahim Birkuti a Muslim cleric critical of Boko Haram, was shot dead by two gunmen on a motorcycle. In July 2011, the Federal government announced its plan to create a panel to initiate negotiations with Boko Haram, which the group rejected. In August 2011, the U.N. headquarters in Abuja was bombed. Boko Haram claimed responsibility for all suicide-bombs where 23 people were killed.

Furthermore, in September 2011, Babakura Fugu, brother-in-law of late-Boko Haram leader Mohammed Yusuf, was shot dead two days after attending a peace meeting with ex-President Olusegun Obasanjo, although Boko Haram denied any involvement in the incident. In November 2011, a series of bomb and gun attacks took place in both Yobe and Borno States. In November 2011, Boko Haram announced that it will not hold talks with the government until all arrested members of its sect, have been released. In December 2011, Boko Haram bombed Saint Theresa Catholic Church in Madalla, Niger State, near Abuja on Christmas Day. One policeman was killed in a failed bomb attack on a church in Jos, Plateau State during the same period. Finally, in January 2012, President Goodluck Jonathan declared a state of emergency in 15 local government areas in Borno, Yobe and Plateau States and closed Nigeria's land borders in the north, while he also accused Boko Haram to have infiltrated Nigeria's government, including the executive, national assembly and judiciary.

Nevertheless, again in January 2012, Boko Haram launched bomb attacks and heavy gun battles in Kano targeting the police headquarters, with 150 people killed. Idegu (2012: p.1 &3) reported that the Boko Haram attacks against Tse and Shong villages in Plateau State reduced the two villages to rubble "with no house standing", with 45 houses burnt and 140 dead. Unfortunately, as the bodies were to be buried the following day, the terrorists attacked again scattering those assembled at the mass burial ground, as well as killing fleeing Senator Gyang Dantong and Honourable Gyang Fulani (Idegu, et. al., 2012: p.1 & 3). Idegu (2012: p.60) further reported that 5,500 people were left displaced in Plateau State, after the Boko Haram attacks.

Boko Haram's attacks became more virulent since May 2013 when President Goodluck Jonathan ordered a military operation to crush the terrorist organization. These include the killing of more than 143 people at a check-point mounted by its guerrillans on the highway between Maiduguri and Damaturu and its night invasion and killing of more than 40 students at University of Agriculture in Yobe State on 29 September 2013 and beheading 8 travelers along the Maiduguri road (Admin., 2013).

Moreover, *Boko Haram's* increasing kidnappings of government officials, foreign nationals and civilians since February 2013 is believed to be the result of greater collaboration between the group and Ansaru, as well as the "Movement for Oneness and Jihad in West Africa" (MUJAO). Boko Haram's collaboration with Ansaru has made it possible for it to benefit from the networks and skills that Ansaru's members developed from training and operating with "Al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb" (AQIM) and MUJAO members in the Sahel region (Zenn, 2013: p.1). Coupled with this link, the National

Counter-terrorism Center (2013) believes that AQIM has been providing direct funding and training for Boko Haram's members.

Moreover, Boko Haram militants' raids of border towns in Borno State using pick-up trucks equipped for desert fighting and the capture of heavily armed Boko Haram members on Algerian borders reveal that the group has or is in the process of linking with "Al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb" (AQIM). This essay therefore stresses that the later defeat of Boko Haram in Mali and Algeria, as well as the group's fear of a possible future defeat in Nigeria, has encouraged it to already forge even stronger ties with other al-Qaeda affiliate-Islamic militants in north-western Africa, with the ominous possibility of launching more devastating attacks against Nigeria and other countries within sub-Saharan Africa.

Boko Haram and the Arab Connection

Omeje (2007: p.99) has attributed most of the insurgencies in Africa, like the Nigeria-Biafra Civil War in the late-1960s, the Ugandan Liberation War in the 1980s, the Eritrean separatist war against Ethiopia, and the civil wars in Liberia, Burundi, Somalia, Angola, DR-Congo, Liberia and Sierra Leone to outside sponsorship. This is true also for Boko Haram.

Therefore, rating the Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria as a local Nigerian terrorist organization may be incorrect. Evidence reveals that the group has international connections with North Africa and the Arab world. Most of its suicide-bombers have been known to be Islamic jihadists imported from other North African states. Analysts have argued that the ingenuity of execution, the impact and the colossal nature of the suicide-bombing of the U.N. Headquarters on 26 August 2011 by Mohammed Abul Barra proves that Boko Haram suicide-bombers are trained by expert terrorist organizations outside Nigeria (eerily reminiscing of the U.N. Headquarters' late-2003 bombing in Baghdad, Iraq).

Some scholars like Johnson (2012) and Perry (2011) have affirmed that Boko Haram has a link with "Al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb" (AQIM) and Somalia's al-Shabaab, which has contributed to the "increasing level of sophistication and organization" of the group. It would not be out of place therefore to say that the group has become a local subsidiary of AQIM, and a fulfillment of AQIM's long-term goal of becoming a regional and global force through the integration of extremist groups from all of North Africa into a single terrorist organization (CSIS, 2010: p.3).

Further, Perry (2011) has reported that Abu Qaqa, Boko Haram's Spokesman has boasted to journalists of sending hundreds of fighters to be trained by al-Shabaab in Somalia. In an interview with the Temple of Praise International Church in Maryland, one of the ex-leaders of Boko Haram, Evangelist Blessed Usman, formerly-Sheik Sani Haliru, confessed that the training of Boko Haram members takes place in Sudan, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, Yemen, Libya, Somalia and Egypt, as well as Niger. He also confessed that he was originally from the Republic of Niger (Usman, 2011).

Moreover, the avowed agenda of Boko Haram to Islamize Nigeria at all cost and the sophistication of its operations prove that the group has international connections with more formidable terrorists organizations outside Nigeria. Johnson (2011) and Ngex (2012) affirm this international connection. For instance, Johnson (2011) reported that Boko Haram has entered an agreement with "...al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb to coordinate and synchronize their efforts". This proves why Usman (2011) in his confession claims that Osama Bin-Laden was his mentor.

Although other scholars including Johnson (2011), Oluwajuyitan (2011) and Tande (2012:2), have argued that economic disparity in Nigeria between the north and south, poverty, political marginalization, social inequality, injustice, corruption and failed government, are all local reasons for the rise of Boko Haram, the group itself has never accepted these reasons as the *raison d'être* for its actions.

This essay stresses that the prevalence of these socio-economic factors in Nigeria does not, in any way, justify the carnage regularly wrought by Boko Haram's terrorist attacks. This violence cannot solve the above problems, but instead creates other problems which the group would not be able to correct afterwards. It may be true to say that Boko Haram is inspired by a global jihadist ideology and is a continuation of a long drawn attempt by the Arab world to Islamize Nigeria and also use Nigeria as a launching pad for international terrorist activities against the West. Boko Haram appears to be the last stage of the Islamization project, which is either going to succeed in changing the secular nature of the Nigerian state or the corporate existence of the country.

The effort to Islamize Nigeria started with the Sharia debate during Nigeria's Second Republic since the late-1970s. The Sharia debate which sparked continued debates about the role of Islam in Nigeria's national life and the country's place in the Muslim world, were sponsored by Northern Nigerian political leaders who have held the reins of power for the greater part of Nigeria's independent existence. These debates have inspired the emergence of extremist Islamic groups that held jihadist ideology. The first orchestrated attempt by Islamic fundamentalists to challenge the secular nature of the Nigerian state came also during the country's Second Republic. Since then, the country has witnessed an upsurge of Islamic radicalism (Tande, 2012: p.5). Other Islamic fundamentalist groups that arose before Boko Haram include the *Talakawas*, *Maitatsine*, *Isawa* Movement, Islam in Africa Organization, *Hezbollah* Movement Nigeria, *Tablib* group, *Kala Kato*, *Yan Izala*, Islamic Movement of Nigeria, Nigerian *Taliban*, *Al Sunna Wal Jamma* and the *Shiite* Organization, etc.

The activities of these groups were heightened during the Third Republic when the Islamic leaders in power at the time formerly registered Nigeria as a member of the Organization of Islamic Conference (O.I.C.). Before this time, Murtala Mohammed's administration had initiated the national Islamization project, but he was assassinated before the plan could come into full fruition. Quoting Omo Omuruyi of the Nairaland Forum (2012), the cabinet of Olusegun Obasanjo that succeeded the government of Murtala regrettably could not push through the Islamization Plan, due to the presence of some "... avid defenders of the secularism in the Supreme Military Council..."

Nairaland Forum (2012) further shows that although Ibrahim Babangida restarted the process of upgrading Nigeria to full membership of the O.I.C. during his tenure as military Head of State, it was Buhari who finally submitted the application to up-grading Nigeria to full membership in the O.I.C. instead of the Observer status it had enjoyed since the Gowon régime. The process was concluded during Babangida's tenure as a civilian Head of State. On his second ascension to power, Babangida silently acquiesced to the status quo by affirming Nigeria's full-fledged membership of the OIC. This further strengthened the Islamization project.

Inspired by global jihadist ideology coupled with internal backing by those in leadership position, more radical Islamic groups who were bent on ensuring the full implementation of the Sharia emerged in the country in the Fourth Republic. This move was further fueled by events outside the country which included the Arab awakening and the Iranian Revolution (Tande, 2012: p.5 & 7). One of such groups was a Shi'a organization, the "Islamic Movement in Nigeria", which beheaded Gideon Alakuta in 1994 for allegedly desecrating the Koran. Unfortunately, the perpetrators of such act in a democratic nation have not been brought to book to date. This was followed by the adoption of the Sharia in Zamfara State in October 1999, followed shortly by 11 other Northern States (Tande, 2011: p.11-12).

Tande (2011: p.16) believes that the economic and political factors that favour the rise of Islamic fundamentalists are the prevalence of a conducive environment that facilitates the growth and "...entrenchment of extremism in Northern Nigeria". The literature on insurgency in Africa in general, and

Boko Haram in particular, seems to ignore the part religion plays in terrorism and thereby obscure the role of Saudi Arabia in sponsoring terrorism through the spread of religious ideology and teaching promoted by the Saudi state. This puritanical religious ideology disseminated during the annual Hajj to Mecca creates an explosive sentiment for violence and extremism among Islamic pilgrims to that Holy land.

Thus, as *Salafi* ideology "...espouses violence against state authority" (CSIS, 2010: p.5), it became the inspiration for *Boko Haram*. Mohammed Yusuf, the founder of *Boko Haram*, studied in Saudi Arabia and on his return to Nigeria, he set up a camp called Afghanistan to train volunteers for a revolution (Perry, 2011: p.2). Yusuf was therefore trained to raise and lead an international terrorist jihad in Nigeria on his return. This has manifested as *Boko Haram*. This, coupled with its sponsorship of the establishment of an Islamic bank in Nigeria makes the Saudi state culpable.

Concluding Remarks and Recommendations

The birth, survival and success of *Boko Haram* to date, unlike past Islamic fundamentalist groups in northern Nigeria, have proved beyond reasonable doubt that it has international links and support outside Nigeria. It is also regrettably, an indication that global jihadist terrorism is spreading into sub-Saharan Africa. Thus, *Boko Haram* could be redefined as an Arab-inspired Islamic fundamentalist terrorist organization, upholding Salafi-jihad ideology and committed to the global jihad ideology of al-Qaeda. According to Geoff Porter, director for the Middle-East and North Africa at Eurasia Group, as quoted by CSIS (2010: p.5), "once someone embraces jihadi ideology and plots or commits terror attacks, regional governments have few tools beyond police action to neutralize them."

Such extremists motivated solely by ideology are less likely to consider any amnesty programs or negotiated political solutions (CSIS, 2010: p.5). *Boko Haram's* refusal to negotiate with the Federal Government (Abdallah, 2012) and the rejection of amnesty by its members (Johnson, 2011) is a clear indication that the group espouses Salafi-jihad ideology. While *Boko Haram* may, in the short-term, be a security threat mostly to Nigeria, the huge security gaps in many sub-Saharan African states heightens the vulnerability of all these countries, especially in the West African sub-region to instability, due to spill-over effect in case of possible escalation and a possible increase in refugee crisis that may cost the international community a fortune in blood and treasure. This is a possibility as long as the bombings and terrorism continues. The arrest of *Boko Haram* members at the Algerian border is a clear proof.

As recommendations to control the *Boko Haram* insurgency, one solution would be to identify its links with international terrorist organizations outside Nigeria and thereby deal with its source of financing with the aim of crippling its "life-wire". Moreover, the Nigerian government should take proactive measures to control the spread of Salafi-jihad ideology by controlling the curricula of Islamic studies in all Almajiris schools and religious departments in local universities in the hope of defining, controlling and enforcing an acceptable interpretation of Islam and a non-violence-inspired training of future Islamic religious clerics. Where possible, the appointment and preaching of Moslem clerics should be also be regulated by the Nigerian government.

Since "conflict prevention, mitigation and response", according to Council on Foreign Relations (2012: p.1) "are global concerns, because instability often spills across borders and triggers piracy, drug trafficking, small-arms sales, environmental exploitation and terrorism", vital multilateral cooperation and action by the international community with the government of Nigeria is necessary to end also the *Boko Haram* menace. This could be further facilitated by the UNDP's Bureau for Crisis-Prevention and Response to circumvent the nationalist principle of non-interference in the internal affairs of affected states. Only close inter-governmental cooperation with the Nigerian government can finally defeat both *Boko Haram* and stem the rise of other regional Islamic fundamentalist insurgencies in the future.

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